

The Impact of Terrorism on Human Development in Iraq

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Abstract

This paper aims to investigate human development that has been impacted by terrorism in Iraq. Iraq has a high level of corruption making it one from the eighth most corrupt country in the world. It has failed to pass effective investment, tax, and property laws to secure both domestic and foreign investment as well as to create effective security forces to protect its infrastructure and businesses. The large disparities in living standards, development failures, high unemployment rates and low standards of living are among the reasons that contributed to encourage terrorism in Iraq. In the light of this problem the study hypothesis represent with "empower people and expand their choices will be an important factor in reducing terrorism and this will make people eager to maintain economic and social investments". The study reached a number of results, the most important of which is the impact of terrorism on the level of human development in Iraq through the analysis of its indicators (education, health and income). We note that it has a negative impact on human development. The human development index was good in the nineties as one of the best levels, the HDI reached its highest value in 1990 (0.712) , that was the highest value for human development in Iraq, and then the value of the HDI was reduced to (0.633) in 2005 , it became (0.642) in 2013. This value puts Iraq among countries with intermediate human development. In the light of the above results the recommendations focused on the need to address the economic, social and political causes of terrorism.

Keywords: Terrorism, Human Development, Iraq.

1. Introduction

In simple words, Terrorism is known as the way to make the people of all over world frighten. Terrorists are those people, who are reason of the terrorism. Nowadays, it is the common problem of across the world. Terrorism can potentially affect economic growth in the short run through a number of channels. Such attacks can increase uncertainty which limits investments and diverts foreign direct investment (FDI). For developing countries, FDI is an important source of saving to fund investment.

Terrorism campaigns lead to government expenditures on defensive actions to harden targets and proactive measures to capture terrorists and their assets. This increased government spending on security can crowd out more growth-enhancing public and private investments (Sandler, 2008).

Terrorism have adverse impacts on the economic growth, these impacts are transmitted through various channels. First and foremost, terrorism

destroys physical and human capital of a country. Terrorism often results in the collapse of health and educational infrastructure; leading to scarcity in the clean drinking

Water and facilities of sanitation, medical care, deterioration in the standard of education, low enrollment rates all of these have negative implications for economic growth. Second, it restricts the trade and business activities leading to restrain the economic growth. Third due to increased perception of risks, terrorism may reduce the inflows of Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) and as FDI is a crucial part in the investment activities in most of the developing countries and any decrease in FDI will reduce the economic growth (ShabirHyder 2015).

In Iraq terrorism has seen at the peak. Terrorism means systematic threat towards development of the economy. From the last few years the terrorism attack affects the progress of Iraq. Our paper is trying to show that terrorism impact on the progress as well as economic condition of Iraq. The economic position of Iraq is totally going to destroy due to terrorism attacks, especially education, health and per capita income, which are the most important axes of human development.

1.1: Problem of the Study: The deterioration of the economic, social and political situation in Iraq led to the emergence of the phenomenon of terrorism,

which resulted in a series of economic, social and political effects, the most prominent of which are the negative effects on development in general and human development in particular, and this prompts the researcher to identify some of these effects.

1.2: Objectives of the Study: we will explore the impact of terrorism on the human development in Iraq through its component:

1. Impact of terrorism on education.
2. Impact of terrorism on the health service.
3. Impact of terrorism on the per capita income.

1.3: Significant of Study: The importance of the study stems from the fact that it is related to the important subject of terrorism to explain the nature, causes and effects on human development in Iraq.

1.4: Study Hypothesis: The study is based on the following hypothesis:

- a. Although overcoming poverty and improving development performance does not guarantee reduced levels of terrorism, put low levels of development are in most cases correlated with terrorism.
- b. Failure to develop can increase the phenomenon of terrorism.

1.5: Conceptual Framework

2. Definition of Terrorism

Terrorism is “the threatened or actual use of illegal force and violence by a non state actor to attain a political, economic, religious, or social goal through fear, coercion, or intimidation.” The victims or objects of terrorist attack have little intrinsic value to the terrorist group but represent a larger human audience whose reaction the terrorists seek.

It is important to understand that terrorists are rational actors. They have a specific purpose for their use of violence and anticipate that it will create a reaction from the audience that they are targeting (Corbin, 2012).

Terrorism is the premeditated use or threat to use violence by individuals or sub national groups in order to obtain a political or social objective through the intimidation of a large audience beyond that of the immediate victims. Terrorists try to make their attacks appear to be random to maximize an audience's anxiety as risks seem ubiquitous. In truth, attacks are not random but planned to exploit perceived target weaknesses and value.

2.1: Division of Terrorism:

Terrorist events are usually subdivided into two varieties:

A. Domestic terrorism: Domestic terrorism is homegrown with consequences for only the host country, its institutions, citizens, property, and policies. As such, domestic terrorism involves perpetrators

Victims and targets solely from the host country. Through its victims, targets, supporters perpetrators, or implications,

b. Transnational terrorism: concerns more than a single country. If the terrorists cross a border to perpetrate their acts, then the attacks are transnational. Terrorist incidents that begin in one country and conclude in another country (e.g., an international skyjacking or the mailing of a letter bomb to another country) are transnational terrorist events (Sandler, 2008).

2.2: Causes of Terrorism

There are number of distinct schools of thought emphasizing the relative importance of certain terrorism determinants on theoretical grounds. Some of these schools are: (Friedrich Schneider, 2011)

1. Some scholars suggest that terrorism is rooted in 'relative' economic deprivation (which manifests itself, e.g., in poverty, within-country inequality and a lack of economic opportunities.

2. Others emphasize the role of socio-economic change over long-run socio-economic conditions. They argue that terrorism is fostered by the process of modernization which creates different types of strain. In general, modernization is associated with economic, demographic and social changes. Terrorist organizations are able to capitalize on the grievances of 'modernization losers', thus making recruitment, financing or other forms of support more likely. Also, terrorist organizations may use modern means of communication to disseminate their opinions more effectively. Modernization is likely to lower the costs of terrorist activity.

3. The political and institutional order is also argued to be connected to terrorism. There is an ongoing academic debate on whether a certain political system (a democratic or autocratic regime) is more prepared to deal with terrorism. While the former can offer non-violent means of voicing dissent, it is also constrained in its efforts to realize 'hard' counter-terrorism. In general, terrorist activity should decrease with higher levels of institutional quality.

4. Political transformation and political instability are also sometimes regarded as causes of terrorism, in particular in popular discourse. Changes in a political system create political vacuums which terrorist groups can use to push their agendas.

5. Violence is also a consequence of civilizational clash. The main idea is that when groups exhibit different identities (e.g., in the sense of different religions or ethnicity), this leads to more conflict either between different groups within a country or between different country groups organized along civilizational lines.

6. Economic and political integration is also sometimes linked to terrorism. On the one hand this view transfers the idea that terrorism is rooted in socio-economic change and conditions to the global arena. That is, if individuals are incited by an existing global order (e.g., the existing global distribution of wealth) that is perceived as 'unfair', it should be easier for terrorist organizations to find support by building on related grievances.

3. The Concept of Human Development

The Human Development Report (HDR) 2010 definition: 'Human development is the expansion of people's freedoms to live long, healthy and creative lives; to advance other goals they have

reason to value; and to engage actively in shaping development and equitably and sustainably on a shared planet. People are both beneficiaries and drivers of human development, as individuals and in groups (deSouza, 2013).

Human development aims to enlarge people's freedoms to do and be what they value and have reason to value. In practice, human development also empowers people to engage actively in development on our shared planet. It is people-centered. At all levels of development, human development focuses on essential freedoms: enabling people to lead long and healthy lives, to acquire knowledge, to be able to enjoy a decent standard of living and to shape their own lives. Many people value these freedoms in and of themselves; they are also powerful means to other opportunities. Human development also encompasses other worthwhile freedoms associated with human well-being in both developing and industrialized nations.

Human development sets priorities among goals using several principles at the same time. Commonly used principles include poverty reduction, equity, efficiency, voice and participation, sustainability respect for human rights and fostering the common good. Human development is multidimensional and its components are interconnected. Thus analyses and policies to advance human development take a holistic view. They identify how powerful means such as economic growth best advance human development across time. They clarify the sequence and type of investments that expand key capabilities most effectively. And they engage in periodic public debate about values and priorities (Alkire, 2010).

3.1: Components of Human Development

The noted Pakistani economist Mahbub ul Haq considered four essential pillars of human development. These are: Human Development: Meaning, Objectives and Components (Mr. Rahul Bhardwaj, 2012).

a. **Equality** If development is viewed in terms of enhancing people's basic capabilities, people must enjoy equitable access to opportunities.

b. **Sustainability**, this means that the term sustainability focuses on the desired balance between future economic growth and environmental quality. To attain the goal of sustainable development, what is of great importance is the attainment of the goal of both intra-generation and inter-generation equality.

This kind of inequality includes the term 'social well-being' not only for the present generation but also for the people who will be on the earth in the future.

c. **Productivity**, Another component of human development is productivity which requires investment in people. This is commonly called investment in human capital. Investment in human capital—in addition to physical capital—can add more productivity.

d. **Empowerment** human development requires empowerment in all aspects of life. Empowerment implies a political democracy in which people themselves make the decisions about their lives. Under it, people enjoy greater political and civil liberties and remain free from excessive controls and regulations. Empowerment refers to decentralization of power so that the benefits of governance are reaped by all peoples.

3.2: Human Development dimensions

Human Development combines three dimensions: (Mr. Rahul Bhardwaj, 2012).

1. A long and healthy life: Life expectancy at birth, Life expectancy at birth, as an index of population health and longevity.
2. Education index: Mean years of schooling and Expected years of schooling, Knowledge and education, as measured by the adult literacy rate (with two-thirds weighting and the combined primary, secondary, and tertiary gross enrollment ratio (with one-third weighting).
3. A decent standard of living: GNI per capita (PPP), as indicated by the natural Logarithm of gross domestic product per capital at purchasing power parity.

4. Terrorism and Human Development

According to the World Bank study, poverty reduction in countries affected by large-scale violence is average. Nearly one percentage point a year is declining than in countries that have not been affected by violence. This "development deficit" is particularly concentrated in fragile and conflict-affected countries.

The lack of development is due to the weakness of the institutions, which will not be able to absorb development inputs, as is the case for countries that were not affected by the conflict. Terrorism is often rooted in contexts of poverty, deprivation, inequality and injustice, social marginalization and weak rule of law. Some global studies refer to that the minimum levels of violent crime are generally linked to the highest levels of development, as well

as to lower levels Of income inequality (UNOCD, 2013).

5. Patterns of Terrorism in Iraq

Contemporary terrorism has many patterns in which it is implemented, including the following patterns:

5.1: Car bombs and bombs

This pattern has a great impact on human development in Iraq because of the high number of

dead and wounded by the explosion of the wheels, bombs and explosive belts. The total number of dead and wounded during the period (2010 - 2014) (15964) dead, and the number of wounded was (51086).

It reached its peak in 2013, the number of people killed (11965), the number of wounded (4950), the number of car bombs (470), the number of explosive devices (344), the number of explosive belts (502) and the number of injuries reached (40627), results are illustrated in the following table:

Table (1): the number of dead and wounded in the explosion of bombs, belts and explosive belts in Iraq for the period (2010-2014).

year	killed people	wounded	car bombs	explosive devices	explosive belts	Others affected
2010	1074	31938	86	42	147	356
2011	747	2011	71	36	7	80
2012	584	2223	120	84	5	224
2013	11965	4950	470	344	502	40627
2014	1594	9964	314	578	29	397
Total	15964	51086	1061	1084	690	41684

Source: The Impact of Terrorism on Human Rights, 2008, , (2003-2008). (2009-2011), (www.protectingecation.org).

5.2: Suicide Terrorism

In this type of terrorism the terrorist sacrifices himself by blowing himself up or blowing up the plane or car he is traveling in, he depends on the use of large quantities of explosives against vital targets packed with people causing the events of the largest number of Civilian casualties (Abdelkafi, 2007). Iraq suffered an increase in suicide bombings after 2003, with 87 attacks, 6

suicide bombings, 347 deaths and 1261 wounded, these figures have risen, peaking in 2007 as a result of the deteriorating security situation.

The number of terrorist attacks reached (1041) and the number of suicide attacks (203). The number of killed (6334) and the wounded (11965) and the number of suicide attacks (682) and the number of dead (24354) And the number of wounded (45172), the following table shows the results:

Table (2): Statistics of Terrorism in Iraq for the Period (2003-2010)

year	Terrorist attacks	Suicide attacks	Dead	Wounded
2003	87	6	347	1261
2004	305	25	2990	3961
2005	619	162	3337	5974
2006	836	95	4591	8256
2007	1041	203	6334	11965
2008	1103	88	2841	6637
2009	1134	53	2573	9373
2010	1176	50	2041	6745
Total	6301	684	24354	45172

Source: (Jassem et al., 2010)

6. The Impact of Terrorism on Human Development in Iraq

Terrorism has a negative impact on human development indicators in Iraq through its direct effects on human security and its threat to life, as well as its indirect impact on people's access to education, health.

6.1: The Impact of Terrorism on Education:

After 2003, education was affected by the country's quantitative and qualitative conditions, including war, security instability, and widespread terrorism, which helped to raise the dropout rate in education, thereby affecting the human development situation through the increase in the dropout rate Because

most of the dropouts from the poor class in Iraqi society and as a result of the displacement of its regions and the state of security instability increased the preparation of dropouts of students.

The number of dropout students in the primary stage increased. The total number of dropouts for the period (2013-2003) reached 928198, reaching a peak of (137188) for the academic year 2003-2004. These numbers decreased slightly in the number of students who dropped out for the period (2006-2008) , And then increased for the academic year (2009-2010), amounted to (134748), while for the secondary stage the total number of dropouts (504053), as the dropout rates for the period (2009-2010), and reached (69860) , the following table shows the results.

Table (3): Leakage of students in the primary and secondary levels in Iraq for the period (2003-2013).

Years	Leakage of students in the primary	Leakage of students in the secondary
2003-2004	137188	45879
2006-2005	101157	52119
2007-2006	125157	63587
2008-2007	103433	47791
2009-2008	105431	48257
2010-2009	134748	69865
2011-2010	12353	63151
2012-2011	109526	54810
2013-2012	99205	58594
Total	928198	504053

Source: (UNDP, 1990-2013), World Bank, 2015, <http://data.albankaldawil.org/indicator/SE.ADT.LITR.ZS>, 2012-2012.

Illiteracy rates were also high during the last two decades, as well as a decrease in literacy rates. The percentage of illiteracy (28%) of the total population aged 10 years and above was significantly different between rural and urban areas (.Republic of Iraq, 2012).

Adult literacy rates for the years (2005-2010) in Iraq dropped to 78.1%. This means that the rate of illiteracy in Iraq is rising from 10% to 21.9%. This rate is significant, affecting the education system. This percentage increased to 22.4% in 2011. Literacy rates reached 77.6% Illiteracy rates were relatively low in 2012, with adult literacy rates increasing to 79%.

Table (4): Literacy and Literacy Rates in Iraq for the Years (2005-2012)

years	Adult literacy rate%	Illiteracy rates as%
2010-2005	78.1	21.9
2011	77.6	22.4
2012	79	21

Source : (Programme, UNDP, 2013), World Bank, 2015, <http://data.albankaldawil.org/indicator/SE.ADT.LITR.ZS>, 2012-2012.

The destruction of the school buildings reached (2751) schools that were destroyed and more than 2400 were stolen. (197) schools, and 238 schools were used as stores of equipment (Al-Azzawi, 2013). After 2003, the number of attacks on universities and schools increased. The Ministry of Education recorded 31600 attacks on schools for

the period 2009-2012. More than 100 school students and 200 university students were killed .The number of attacks increased in 2011, it became (29) attacks ,and the number of dead (106). During 2013 the number of attacks increased to be (56) attacks, the following table show the results:

Table (5): Number of dead from school students in Iraq for the period (2008-2012)

Duration	Dead	Wounded
2008	28	-
2009	4	12
2010	49	26
2011	37	33
2012	69	167
2013	12	-
Total	199	238

Source: Global Coalition to Protect Education from Attack, 2014.

As for higher education, the infrastructure of colleges and universities and educational institutions has been damaged and stolen with 84%. Teachers and students became a direct target of terrorism (UNESCO, 2010-2014).

The Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research said that more than (534) professors were killed, wounded, detained and kidnapped by terrorist acts for the period (2003-2012), the share

of Baghdad University was the most followed by Mustansiriya University, and the students of these universities received their share of terrorism (62%) have a doctorate degree and a third of them are specialists in medicine and science, and more than 335 university students were among the students Killed, wounded and missing as a result of the attack on Iraqi universities during the years 2003-2008, the following table shows the results.

Table (6): The number of dead from Iraqi university students For the period (2003-2011)

year	Dead	Wounded
2008-2003	256	46
2011-2009	20	115
Total	276	161

Source: (Iraq, 2008, 2010, 2011, 2012, 2014-2013), (www.protecting.ca.org)

Attacks on university professors continued after 2003 and resulted in the killing of at least 299 teachers in various scientific disciplines and those who hold high scientific degrees, which reflected the negative effects of the phenomenon of terrorism

on higher education, the high frequency of assassinations against professors during the period 2006-2007. This percentage decreased in 2008, the following table shows the results.

Table (7): Number of academics who were subjected to assassinations for the period (2003 – 2010)

year	Assassination
2003	10
2004	31
2005	44
2006	86
2007	47
2008	6
2009	10
2010	

Source: (Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research, 2009)

6.2: The Impact of Terrorism on Health

Iraq used to have one of the best health services in the region. But expenditure cuts, neglect and poor management over the last 15 years have taken a heavy toll. The looting and destruction of health facilities that took place after the war, the interruption of electricity and water supplies and the security problems have caused a further deterioration in services.

After 2003, the health system deteriorated due to the terrorist attacks that negatively impacted the health sector in Iraq. Doctors became vulnerable to

murder and kidnapping, forcing many doctors to leave Iraq in the period 2004-2007, the Iraqi Ministry of Health reported 12 Iraqi hospitals leaving (1243) specialized physicians. This number decreased in 2007 to 1166 specialized physicians, representing a percentage of 94% in 2004, 78% in 2007, and a percentage for the period (2003-2007), (143%) of the departures.

A large number of doctors and health workers were killed and abducted. Attacks reached a peak between two years (2004-2007) due to the deterioration of the security situation. The number of attacks against doctors was 80-90%.

Table (8): Preparation of doctors departing, dead and abducted in Iraq for the period (2003-2011)

years	departing	dead	abducted
2003	12000	2000	250
2004	1500	250	300
2005	3000	150	350
2006	1953	233	-
2008	2000	20000	250
2011	567	2000	250
Total	21020	24633	1400

source: www.Brookings.edu/iraqindex,2003.(Gilbert), (Nabil, 2013).

6.3: The impact of terrorism on GDP

The average per capita income declined in 2003 as a result of the US occupation of Iraq, which paralyzed the economic movement in the country and stopped the oil exports because of the military operations, which caused the decrease in half, but then it was rebounded as a result of the lifting of

sanctions and the resumption of oil exports and increase, The average per capita income rose from (415.5) dollars in 2003 to reach (3375) dollars in 2008. Global financial crises, in 2009 and that caused the decline Oil prices reflected the negative impact on the average income which reached (2977) dollars, re-increase after 2010 reached (3606) dollars.

Table (9): Average per capita income of GDP in Iraq

years	Average per capita income of GDP (dollars)	Average per capita GDP growth rate
2003	415.5	41.0-
2004	993.7	125.0
2005	1296.1	26.2
2006	1890.8	56.0
2007	2501.0	31.0
2008	3375.8	44.0
2009	2977.3	-7.0
2010	3606.3	8.0
2011	4727.1	35.4
2012	5386.4	-6.1
2013	5588.5	-6.1
2014	6200	-

Source: (Fund, 2015) ,(Fund, 2008),(Central Bank of Iraq, 2013)

6.4: The Impact of Terrorism on Human Development in Iraq

Terrorism has a significant impact on human development through the analysis of indicators of human development (education, health and income) in Iraq. This is indicated by the United Nations human development reports through the statement of the value of the Human Development Index for the period (1990-2005-2013).

The level of human development in Iraq was good in the nineties and was at the best levels, the value

of the Human Development Index to the highest value in 1990 (0.712) and is the highest value for human development in Iraq,

Iraq was among the group of countries with high human development, and then the value of HDI was reduced to (0.633) for (2005) because of the conditions that the country is developing. Iraq has become a medium human development country and the value of the human development index has increased to reach (0.642) for the year (2013). This value puts Iraq among countries with intermediate human development.

Table (10): Value of Human Development Indicators in Iraq for the Period (1990-2013)

years	Health indicator	Education indicator	Income indicator	value of the HDI
1990	0.666	0.890	0.607	0.712
2005	0.733	0.715	0.427	0.633
2010	0.783	0.722	0.598	0.629
2013	0.733	0.75	0.671	0.645

Source: (UNDP, 1990-2013), (planning, 2012)

Table (11): Human Development Index for Iraq (2005-2014)

years	Human Development Index
2005	0.621
2006	0.564
2007	0.567
2008	0.632
2009	0.576
2010	0.683
2011	0.639
2012	0.641
2013	0.642
2014	0.654

Source:(UNDP, 2014)

7. Conclusions and Recommendations

7.1: Conclusions

1. Economic growth could reduce political confrontation, military conflicts.
2. The economy cannot work and develop without a secure and stable environment
3. Human development promotion is one of the main strategies that lead to decrease terrorism activities, contribute to economic growth,

community development and poverty reduction in developing countries.

4. Terrorism has had a negative impact on overall human development in Iraq through:

- a. Increasing the rate of deterioration in education by increasing the number of dropouts.
- b. Terrorism has increased the rates of illiteracy, Low spending on education, destruction of infrastructure of schools, universities and scientific institutes.
- c. Terrorism has led to a lower level of health services provided to the citizen with the increasing

migration of doctors as a result of frequent killings and threats.

5. The HDI reached its highest value in 1990 (0.712) , that was the highest value for human development in Iraq, then became (0.642) in 2013. This value puts Iraq among countries with intermediate human development.

7.2: Recommendations

To reduce the impact of terrorism on human development in Iraq we suggest:

1. Establish secure and stable environment.
2. Put human development strategy to promote economic growth ,decrease terrorism activities, contribute to poverty reduction.
3. Reduce illiteracy rates in the country.
4. Reduce the proportion of the poor population of the total population, using various economic and non-economic means, because poverty is one of the factors leading to the occurrence of terrorism.
5. Increase the proportion of health expenditure of GDP.
6. There is need of peaceful environment for the foreign investors.
7. Reduce the proportion of military expenditure of GDP, and shift the difference to spending on health and education services.
8. Pay more Attention to the industrial and agricultural sectors through rehabilitation them to reduce the dependence on oil in the life of the citizen.

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